

A revised understanding of the influence of the variance of spatial weights on the Getis-Ord statistic

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Summary

Geospatial hotspot statistics measure concentration in space. One of the most popular such methods is the Getis-Ord statistic, a measure for revealing geographical structure in the tails of an attribute value distribution. The original 1995 paper introducing this measure includes an interpretation of how the variance of the spatial weights employed feeds into the local measures, but the corresponding mathematical expression can be shown to be erroneous. The current paper corrects this expression and discusses the implications of the revised term for the link between the Getis-Ord statistic and the local variances of the spatial weights.

KEYWORDS: Getis-Ord statistic, hotspot statistics, spatial weights, spatial autocorrelation, exploratory spatial data analysis.

1 Introduction

Hotspot statistics allow quantification of geographic accumulations. Several variants of these statistics have been formulated, including measures addressing geometric locations (Kulldorff, 1997), flows (Berglund and Karlström, 1999; Tao and Thill, 2019), spatio-temporal arrangements (Wang and Lam, 2020), incremental cluster growth (Aldstadt and Getis, 2006), scale-stratified analysis (Westerholt et al., 2015), mutual influence of low and high-value clusters (Zhang and Lin, 2006), and controlling for global autocorrelation when searching local hotspots (Ord and Getis, 2001). Keith Ord and Arthur Getis introduced G_i^* (Ord and Getis, 1995; Getis and Ord, 1992), which has become a quasi-standard for quantifying high and low attribute value clustering. While the statistic itself is now routinely used in exploratory spatial data analysis, the 1995 article contains a section that introduces a better understanding of the normalising denominator of the statistic and links G_i^* to Moran's I . This short paper proposes a correction of a mathematical expression that was originally erroneously stated in the said part of the original paper and discusses the implications of this correction for the interpretation of G_i^* .

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2 The local Getis-Ord and Moran statistics

The statistics relevant for the present contribution are global (Cliff and Ord, 1981, p. 17) and local Moran's I (Anselin, 1995), and G_i^* (Ord and Getis, 1995). Setting $z_i = (x_i - \bar{x})/s$, these are given as

$$I = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij} z_i z_j}{W}, \quad (1a)$$

$$I_i = z_i \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij} z_j, \quad (1b)$$

$$G_i^* = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij} x_j - W_i^* \bar{x}}{s \sqrt{(nS_{1i}^* - W_i^{*2}) / (n-1)}}, \quad (2)$$

with w_{ij} denoting spatial weights linking sites i and j , x_i and x_j being n real-valued samples with mean \bar{x} and standard deviation s , and $W = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij}$ and $W_i^* = \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij}$ being the overall and row-wise sums of spatial weights. Moran's I , when standardised, is asymptotically normal in the null hypothesis (the distribution depends strongly on the weights for small samples, see Westerholt (2022, p. 45 ff.)). G_i^* comes in standardised form and is thus approximately normal.

3 Corrected expression for the variance of local spatial weights

Ord and Getis in their 1995 paper (page 289) define a term $K_{ri} = \sum_{j=1}^n (w_{ij} - \bar{w}_i)^r / (n-1)$, with $\bar{w}_i = W_i^*/n$. For $r = 2$, this term is an estimator for the variance of the local spatial weights. After algebraic transformations, the authors obtain the term $K_{2i} = (nS_{1i}^* - W_i^{*2}) / (n-1)$, which equals the expression under the square root in the denominator of equation 2. However, it can be shown that this expression is incorrect by a factor of $1/n$. The corrected term is given as

$$K_{2i} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (w_{ij} - \bar{w}_i)^2}{(n-1)} = \frac{S_{1i}^* - \frac{2}{n} W_i^{*2} + \frac{1}{n} W_i^{*2}}{n-1} = \frac{(nS_{1i}^* - W_i^{*2})}{n(n-1)}. \quad (3)$$

In a brief aside, Ord and Getis (1995, p. 289) also use the expression K_{2i} for linking G_i^* to Moran's I . This link also needs to be corrected accordingly. Using the corrected term from equation 3, and writing the numerator of equation 2 as $\sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij} (x_j - \bar{x})$, global and local Moran's I can be expressed in terms of weighted G_i^* values as

$$I = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n z_i \sqrt{n \cdot K_{2i}} G_i^*}{W}, \quad (4a)$$

$$I_i = z_i \sqrt{n \cdot K_{2i}} G_i^*. \quad (4b)$$

Expressing Moran’s I by G_i^* is convenient if one has already calculated G_i^* (and thus K_{2i}). The link between the two measures also shows that the two statistics are inherently interrelated and why, therefore, mapped local Moran’s I and G_i^* values often flag similar areas as significant. However, according to the above findings, these similarities depend to some extent on both n and the local variances of the spatial weights.

4 The role of the variance of local spatial weights in the Getis-Ord statistic

The K_{ri} terms in the original paper mainly serve the purpose of defining higher order moments of the distribution of G_i^* . However, equation 3 also implies a modified understanding of the influence of the spatial weights on G_i^* : the denominator of G_i^* does not include the square root of the variance of the local weights, as was originally stated, but the square root of n times this variance. Especially for highly irregular spatial units, the impact of the variability of the weights on G_i^* can therefore vary considerably across space. The normalisation of G_i^* is then determined to a large extent by the excess contribution of the variance of the weights. Moreover, the ratio of n times the variance of the weights to the standard deviation of the attribute grows by a factor of \sqrt{n} , and so does the slope of this ratio over the variance of the weights. The influence of the local variances of the weights is thus particularly pronounced when a data set is large and when the attribute variance is numerically small. The difference between the previous and the corrected interpretations of the denominator of G_i^* is best illustrated by a real-world example.

The following demonstration is based on a Twitter data set from London and the attribute is LDA-topic association (see Steiger et al. (2015) for more details). Figure 1 shows the ratios between the standard deviations of the spatial weights and the attribute standard deviation. Each subplot corresponds to a spatial weighting scheme (B, C, W; see Bavaud (2014)). In each of the graphs, the erroneous and corrected versions of the variance of the weights are contrasted. In all the diagrams we see that the slopes of the approximated straight lines have greatly increased by the inclusion of the factor \sqrt{n} . The influence of the weights thus grows quicker as originally anticipated when the weights show large variability. Moreover, oftentimes, the local standard deviations of the spatial weights weigh substantially more than the standard deviation of the attributes. This is not nearly as pronounced when using the uncorrected expression from the original paper (see the diamond graphs at the bottom of each diagram). It is therefore to be expected that in many real applications the variability of the spatial weights will dominate the normalising denominator of G_i^* .

5 Conclusions

This short paper addresses the influence of the local variances of the spatial weights on the hotspot measure G_i^* . It was shown that the inclusion of these variance terms in the definition of G_i^* was misinterpreted due to an erroneous expression in the original 1995 paper. After correcting this error and the corresponding relationship between G_i^* and Moran’s I , a discussion was carried out on how and when the variance of spatial weights can affect the normalising denominator of the statistic. The difference between the previous and the revised understanding was demonstrated using a Twitter sample. The revised understanding of how much the variance of the weights affects

Figure 1: Ratios of local standard deviations of the spatial weights and the standard deviation of the attribute. All plots are for $n = 671$ and show these ratios for the uncorrected (diamonds) and the corrected expressions (circles). The sub-diagrams are for (a) binary (B), (b) globally normalised (C), and (c) row-standardised (W) spatial weights.

G_i^* is relevant for the correct interpretation of the measure. In addition, a more in-depth analysis of the interaction between G_i^* and different types of spatial weights is needed. Given the widespread use of G_i^* , such results may provide important insights practically and theoretically, and this short paper aims to motivate this kind of follow-up research.

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Biography

René Westerholt is Juniorprofessor and head of the Spatial Modelling Lab at TU Dortmund University (Germany). His research interests are focused on geographic information science (with foci on urban analytics and formalising space and place) and spatial statistics (focusing on exploratory spatial analysis methods). Before coming to Dortmund, he held a post as Assistant Professor at the University of Warwick (UK). René completed his PhD in geography at Heidelberg University (Germany), after obtaining his Bachelor's and Master's degrees in geoinformatics at Osnabrück University (Germany).

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